

Laboratory and pilot scale production of biogas from different biomass

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Exploration of potentialities of different plant-biomass for biogas generation had been examined. Biogas generation had been found to be considerable with different biomass mixed with dung samples as inoculum. However, the biogas generation had been found to be dependent on the extent of pulverisation, pH and other physical conditions. Biogas generation in pilot scale biogas digesters using water hyacinth with cow dung (*gobar*) had been observed to be satisfactory.

Exploration of non-conventional energy sources for the generation of energy is an imperative need for a developing country like India. In view of enormous reserve of renewable biomass, the conversion of energy from biomass appears to be the most desirable energy option¹ in India. This consideration led us to study different aspects of biogas generation². Use of biomass for generation of fuel means sound and healthy waste management, generation of clean fuel and production of slurry for use as fertilizer.

The biogas production from *Gobar* has been used extensively³. *Gobar* is an ideal biomass rich in C-content (about 9.0–9.5% of the total mass) and is present as adequately homogenized mass to be converted into gas by anaerobic digestion. Other dung samples and human excreta can be similarly treated. Huge quantity of biomass coming from terrestrial ecosystems and residues of agricultural remains from crops after harvest can be recycled for the conversion of energy and minimization of pollution. The economics of the biogas plant utilizing the locally available organic substrates like raw jute sticks, banana stem, water hyacinth, perthenium, municipal and market was wastes, sewage etc. should be assessed.

The use of seasonal raw jute sticks should be precluded as the procurement, crushing and grinding for pre-treatment are costly. The banana stem is available in plenty in India. Production of methane for the biogasification of banana peeling (BP) and *Ipomea fistulosa* (IFL) and their 75 : 25 mixture had been reported to be good⁴ but the commercial viability has not been explored. Municipal wastes, an unending sources of biomass, contain garbage (or food organic wastes) along with roughage content, ash and soils. The separation of these wastes proved to be costly, and unless

proper care is taken to isolate organic wastes from roughage contents (50–60% of total), biogas production can not be regarded to be suitable choice. Market wastes are rich in biodegradable substrates and have high potentiality for biogas production. These were subjected to biomethanation in a 25L-capacity laboratory scale digesters for 75 days. The production of biogas was reported to be 35L/kg at 20 days of hydraulic retention time. But the economics of production and other details are lacking⁵.

In addition to market wastes and sewage, other important plant biomass which are widely available and easily producible are water hyacinth, perthenium (available during rainy seasons and after), aquatic plant hydrilla (available during the rainy season) and other local weeds, which can be utilized for biogas generation. Relatively good methane production from these biodegradable plant materials under different experimental conditions in vials⁶ suggests the potentiality of these materials for biomethanation but the commercial viability of these biomass cannot be ascertained.

For the continuous and economic running of a digester of moderate capacity, the biomass requirement is quite large. Therefore, search for weeds and plant materials, fairly available throughout the year is desirable. These consideration led us to analyze water content of raw biomass and C, N, water and ash content of different air-dried biomass to examine their suitability as substrates for biomethanation. In order to comprehend biomethanation in a better way, biomethanation experiments were carried out in special glass or aspirator bottles of 5-litre and 2-litre capacities using different biomass as substrates under varying conditions. Pilot plants were also constructed for biogas generation us-

ing mixed biomass (water hyacinth and cow dung). The result of our experiments and conclusions derived from these experiments form the subject matter of this paper.

Results and Discussion

The water content of the different fresh plant biomass and moisture content, organic matter and carbon content, N-content, ash content of different air-dried plant biomass were estimated following the procedure suggested by Humphries⁷. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl method. The organic carbon content was estimated by dividing the total organic matter by 1.724 on the assumption that the plant organic matter contains roughly 58% carbon. Analytical data of the biomass are given in Tables 1 and 2.

proximately 5, 8, 10, 12 and 20 wt% of solid biomass estimated by drying the slurry and heating to 120° for 1h) of sun-dried biomass were taken. They were subjected to biomethanation in closed aspirator bottles using added inoculum (like Gobar, goat dung etc.) or without added inoculum in presence or absence of sunlight. The aspirator bottles were made air-tight with rubber corks, properly sealed having outlet and inlet tubes for gas collection and passing inert gas like N₂. The openings were properly closed with pinch corks.

The production of biogas was fairly appreciable from 3 to 6 days depending on the pulverisation of biomass. The collection of gas was made over water in closed eudiometer

Table 1. Physicochemical data of different plants on the basis of air-dried samples*

Plants	% Moisture	% Organic content	% Carbon content	% N	% Water from fresh plant
<i>Eichhornia</i> sp.	10.14	82.50	47.85	1.66	89.59
<i>Parthenium hirsutum</i>	14.47	83.25	48.29	5.39	82.84
<i>Cassia sopheria</i>	11.87	82.83	48.04	3.74	67.55
<i>Cassia fristula</i>	12.05	75.90	44.02	4.49	62.52
<i>Solanum torvum</i>	14.34	72.96	42.32	3.32	86.66
<i>Croton bonplandianum</i>	13.00	76.75	44.51	1.52	77.71
<i>Jatropha gradiflora</i>	18.55	67.38	39.08	4.15	87.51
Green coconut	18.16	79.57	46.16	—	60.45
<i>Calotropis metel</i>	8.34	85.41	48.91	3.45	82.60
<i>Clerodendron viscosum</i>	3.96	92.43	53.61	2.41	72.84
<i>Cestrum diarnum</i>	7.00	91.36	52.99	3.52	77.95
<i>Lantana camara</i>	5.00	89.56	51.95	1.47	63.37
<i>Jatropha rotleri</i>	6.30	87.43	50.71	1.66	77.17
<i>Ipomea impetance</i>	4.80	85.94	49.85	1.93	69.46

* Average of 5 sets of measurement.

Table 2. Water and ash content determination*

Biomass	Water content %	Ash content %
Cow dung	82.0	4.8
Buffalo dung	81.2	5.5
Goat dung	59.3	10.6
Piggery wastes	61.3	9.7
Poultry wastes	76.0	6.0
Water hyacinth	84.0	3.8
Parthenium sp.	49.0	18.8

* Average of 5 sets of measurement

Production of biogas using aspirator bottles :

The green water hyacinth were chopped, pulverised (after elimination of roots) and made into slurry with sufficient amount of water containing calcium carbonate to make the solution alkaline (pH 7.5–8.0). Different concentrations (ap-

proximately 5, 8, 10, 12 and 20 wt% of solid biomass estimated by drying the slurry and heating to 120° for 1h) of sun-dried biomass were taken. They were subjected to biomethanation in closed aspirator bottles using added inoculum (like Gobar, goat dung etc.) or without added inoculum in presence or absence of sunlight. The aspirator bottles were made air-tight with rubber corks, properly sealed having outlet and inlet tubes for gas collection and passing inert gas like N₂. The openings were properly closed with pinch corks.

Biogas production was appreciable even during night and the pressure created was sufficient to remove the rubber corks. The gas production was appreciable even after 25 days after which it decreased. Accurate quantification of gas produced, however, could not be made and the analysis was rather qualitative. The percentage of methane was 45–57% from 7–10 days upto 20–24 days. The study was discontinued after 30 days. The other substrates (biomass) were similarly treated and anaerobic digestions were carried out. The

results were more or less similar but the yield of gas (% CH₄) was different for different biomass. The yield of biogas was higher with water hyacinth or hydrilla.

Biogasification of market wastes at low biomass concentration (upto 10% solid) :

Methane production with sun-dried market wastes with cow dung (*gobar*) as inoculum had been found to be good (55–60% CH₄). However, mucilegenous substances, if present, abnormally reduces the CH₄ production. Pulverization increased biogas production which became maximum usually within 9–12 days depending on the condition of the experiment. The pHs of the media were usually 8.0–8.5 initially which dropped gradually and became 6.4–6.8 within 15–18 days with concomitant decrease in CH₄ production. The change in C-content was only 5–6% after 10 days and increased with the degree of pulverization. Once charged, the gas formation continued for a long time.

The sun-dried and pulverized market wastes (15 and 20 wt%) with inoculum were also subjected to biomethanation. However, the conversion of waste to biogas was low.

Biogas generation and the performance of 4m³ capacity floating dome gas plant at Chandannagar :

Semi-commercial generation of biogas using water hyacinth, perthenium and sewage in plastic digesters had been reported⁸. Commercial generation of biogas were made using mixed biomass [water hyacinth and *Gobar* (10–15%)] in 4 m³ capacity floating dome digester.

Initially 1500 kg of organic biomass (water hyacinth), after elimination of roots and proper chopping was sun-dried for a few days to increase the carbon content and was then charged into the digester. 10–15 kg of *Gobar*, used as seed, formed the base and water hyacinth and *Gobar* (10%) was used in alternate layers. Enough water with little *Gobar* was then added and the mixture was made alkaline (pH~8) using lime water. No stirring was made. Gas production was slow initially and started after an average hydraulic retention period of 30 days. A 'Toshniwal' gas flow-meter (wet type) was used to measure the flow of gas. The flow-meter is good up to a pressure of 8" water column. An average of 2 m³ of biogas was produced per day. The methane content of the gas was approximately 65%. To run the plant continuously 60–75 kg of sun-dried biomass (*Gobar* content was considerably reduced or discontinued) was added to the digester twice a week. The ideal temperature appeared to be 35–40°. However, no temperature control was made and the temperature was dependent on weather; considerable fall in gas generation was noted in winter. The pH was found to be lowered with time but the pH was controlled between 7 and 8. Homogeneous mixing of the materials appeared to be

very much helpful. Aerobic pre-digestion for 5–7 days in homogenizing the biomass was found to be helpful indecoating waxlike bacterial inhibiting surface material surrounding the linear molecules of cellulose and in increasing the rate of digestion.

The biogas plant :

The 4 m³ capacity floating gas holder biogas plant of vertical type was made mainly following the model developed by Renewable Research Institute, Gujarat.⁹ The gas holder assembly consisted of a central guide frame, a drum made of 5 mm thick mild steel sheets and a gas outlet. The drum was kept upside down on the digester so that it dips in the slurry of the biomass and rested on a ledge constructed inside the digester. It collects gas which comes out of the slurry and moves up. When the gas outlet was opened, the collected gas was pushed out by the weight of the drum itself at a constant pressure of 8–10 cm water column. The drum then moves down. This up and down movement of the drum was guided by a central guide pipe fitted in a frame which was fixed to the digester wall. The estimated cost of the plant was Rs. 28000 in September, 1991. So, cost/m³ was Rs. 7000.

Fixed dome biogas plant :

A 3 m³ capacity fixed dome type biogas plant (Janata model) was also constructed near the floating biogas plant. It was an improved version of the Chinese fixed dome biogas plant. It was mainly constructed to compare the merits, demerits, efficiency and costing of two types of biogas plant. The fixed dome biogas unit was entirely a masonry structure. It dispensed with the use of a steel gas holder. Both gas holder and digester formed a combined unit. The estimated cost of this plant was Rs. 18000 in 1993. Cost/m³ was Rs. 6000.

Comparison of floating and fixed dome type biogas unit is presented in Table 3

	Floating type	Fixed dome type
Capital Cost	High	Low
Maintenance cost	High	Low
Release of gas	At constant pressure	At variable pressure causing reduction in efficiency
Location of defects in the gas holder and repairing	Easy	Difficult

Summary :

Some of the generalizations of our experiments are given below. (i) Carbon content of the plant materials is usually

low (3–7% of the total mass). The use of plant materials requires cutting the roots and chopping them into appropriate sizes. Nearly homogenized slurry increases biogas production. The greater the pulverization, the greater will be the biogas generation. Sun-drying should be made to increase the C-content of the biomass. (ii) A solid biomass concentration of 6–8 wt% or at best 10 wt% usually have good result. Higher biomass concentration is not suitable for anaerobic digestion. The digested sludge becomes sticky with increase in the concentration of solid biomass and the gas production decreases. The biogas production requires considerable amount of water, but excess of water should be avoided. It definitely lowers gas production as the concentration of biomass per unit volume of slurry decreases resulting in the decrease in fermentation. But water content must be sufficiently high (85–90%). (iii) pH of the slurry decreases with time depending on experimental conditions and biomass selected and biogas generation decreases. pH should be increased and optimum pH should be maintained at 7.5–8.0 for maximum biogas generation. (iv) Sunlight usually increases biogas generation. Optimal temperature of 35–40° appears to be desirable. Gas generation decreases at higher and lower temperatures. (v) Gas generation increases if plant biomass (like water hyacinth, hydrilla etc.) is mixed with *Gobar* or dung samples. But no appreciable increase is observed with mixed plant biomass. The biomass containing mucilage substance gives low yield of gas. (vi) Anaerobic digestion of biomass first digested with acid (dil. H₂SO₄) for 1 h and subsequently digested with alkali (pH 8–9) increases the yield considerably. However, fresh inoculum like *Gobar*, buffalo dung etc. is to be added before anaerobic digestion.

The observations may be helpful for biogas generation in the commercial or semicommercial scale.

Cost analysis and conclusions :

Approximate size of a biogas plant for a family of five members can be worked out as under : cooking requires 1.25 m³ gas daily; one lamp for 5 h requires 0.65 m³ gas daily; total consumption of gas/day is 2 m³; thus 3–4 m³ capacity biogas plant will meet the demand.

Considerable biomass is required for the purpose and the construction of biogas plants appears costly. The digested slurry can be utilized as fertilizer and its cost cannot be calculated. Naturally, effective cost analysis of biogas generation is difficult. Plenty of biomass like water hyacinth, algae and other plant materials are available. The biomass along with 15–20% dung samples may be utilized by the individual families residing near the source of biomass and agricultural fields for disposal of digested slurry. But to make the biogas plant acceptable to the common people, major thrust should be to reduce the cost of the plant. Moreover, since the anaerobic digestion is a slow process, percentage conversion of C-content to CH₄ is low >> 20%. The two-stage digester system may be utilized for greater conversion of C to CH₄ and may be profitable. But in view of pollution control, waste management, production of bio-fertilizers and clean fuel, biogas generation from biomass should be pursued in right earnest.

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